

The algebra generated by Toeplitz operators with sums of coordinate powers on the Hardy space over the bidisk

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Abstract

We study Toeplitz operators T_p on the Hardy space over the bidisk with symbols of the form $p(z, w) = z^k + w^l$. Although the problem of describing reducing subspaces of Toeplitz operators is infinite-dimensional and analytic in nature, we show that in this case it can be completely reduced to a finite-dimensional algebraic structure. More precisely, we prove that the von Neumann algebra $\mathcal{V}^*(p)$ generated by T_p is $*$ -isomorphic to $M_{kl}(\mathbb{C}) \oplus M_{kl}(\mathbb{C})$. As a consequence, we obtain a complete classification of the minimal reducing subspaces of T_p , which are explicitly described in terms of polynomial data.

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1 Introduction

Let X be a closed subspace in a Hilbert space. Then X is said to be invariant under an operator A if $AX \subset X$. Moreover, X is called a reducing subspace of an operator A if X is invariant under both A and its adjoint A^* . If the only nonzero reducing subspace contained in X is X , then X is said to be minimal. If f is a function in the Hilbert space, $[f]_A$ denotes the smallest reducing subspace of A containing f . We consider a problem determining reducing subspaces and the minimal reducing subspaces in the Hardy space on the bidisk; the precise definition of this space is as follows.

Let \mathbf{T}^2 be the torus and $L^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ be the usual Lebesgue space with respect to the normalized Lebesgue measure dm on \mathbf{T}^2 . Let $H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ be the Hardy space which consists of functions f in $L^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ whose Fourier coefficients $\hat{f}(n_1, n_2) = 0$ if $n_1 < 0$ or $n_2 < 0$.

Let \mathbf{D}^2 be the bidisk. We introduce the Hardy space $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ over the bidisk, which is isometrically isomorphic to $H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$. A function f is in $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ if f is analytic on \mathbf{D}^2 and satisfies the condition

$$\sup_{0 < r \leq 1} \left\{ \int_{\mathbf{T}^2} |f(rz, rw)|^2 dm \right\} < \infty,$$

where dm is the normalized Lebesgue measure on \mathbf{T}^2 .

We note that the reproducing kernel for $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ is the Cauchy kernel

$$K_{(z,w)}(z', w') = \frac{1}{(1 - \bar{z}z')(1 - \bar{w}w')}$$

for $(z, w) \in \mathbf{D}^2$ and $(z', w') \in \mathbf{T}^2$.

Let P be the orthogonal projection from $L^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ onto $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$. Then P is of the form

$$Pf(z, w) = \int_{\mathbf{T}^2} f(z', w') \overline{K_{(z,w)}(z', w')} dm$$

for $f \in L^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$. $L^\infty(\mathbf{T}^2)$ denotes the Banach algebra of all essentially bounded measurable functions with respect to dm . For $\varphi \in L^\infty(\mathbf{T}^2)$, we define the Toeplitz operator with symbol φ as $T_\varphi f = P(\varphi f)$ for $f \in H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$. Using the Cauchy kernel, we can write the Toeplitz operator as

$$T_\varphi f(z, w) = \int_{\mathbf{T}^2} \varphi(z', w') f(z', w') \overline{K_{(z,w)}(z', w')} dm$$

Let p be a polynomial. We define the von Neumann algebra generated by T_p as $\mathcal{W}^*(p)$, and its commutant algebra as $\mathcal{V}^*(p)$. It is known that $\mathcal{V}^*(p)$ is equal to the von Neumann algebra generated by the orthogonal projections onto the reducing subspaces of T_p .

We denote shift operators on the two-variable Hardy space by S_1, S_2 , where $S_1 = T_z$ and $S_2 = T_w$. We will refer to subspaces that are invariant under both S_1 and S_2 as shift-invariant subspaces. In the one-variable case, the invariant subspaces of the shift operator are explicitly determined by the famous Beurling theorem. Consequently, one may ask for a classification or an explicit description of all shift-invariant subspaces; however, such a complete characterization appears to be out of reach. In response to this difficulty, shift-invariant subspaces have been studied under various additional conditions. For instance, Manderkar [9] investigates the condition under which a shift-invariant subspace of $H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ is of the form $qH^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$, where q is an inner function. Moreover, considerable attention has been devoted to related questions. In particular, many mathematicians have investigated common invariant subspaces and reducing subspaces of Toeplitz operators with polynomial symbols. For example, Seto, Nakazi, and the author [7] study shift-invariant subspaces of $H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ that are invariant under Toeplitz operators with non-analytic symbols. In the setting of the weighted Hardy space over the bidisk, the author [5, 6] studies common reducing subspaces of operators $T_{z^{N_1}}$ and $T_{w^{N_2}}$ and reducing subspaces of the Toeplitz operator $T_{z^{N_1} w^{N_2}}$, respectively. Gu [3] generalizes the result and determine common reducing subspaces in the weighted Hardy space over the polydisk. Dan and Huang [2] determine reducing subspaces of multiplication operator defined by $z^k + w^l$ in the Bergman space over the bidisk. Guo and Wang [4] give an abstract criterion for the reducibility of tensor sums of weighted shifts; however, they do not describe the structure of the reducing subspaces.

In this paper we study Toeplitz operators T_p with $p(z, w) = z^k + w^l$ on $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$, and obtain a complete description of their minimal reducing subspaces together with the decomposition $\mathcal{V}^*(p) \cong M_{kl}(\mathbf{C}) \oplus M_{kl}(\mathbf{C})$. Before we proceed to the main theorem, we present some specific examples of invariant subspaces of T_{z+w} . For Toeplitz operators with separable or linear symbols, the tensor product structure of $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ provides a natural framework for constructing shift-invariant subspaces. For example, if θ_1 and θ_2 are one-variable inner functions, subspaces of the form $\theta_1(z)H^2(\mathbf{D}) \otimes \theta_2(w)H^2(\mathbf{D})$ play a fundamental role in the analysis of shift-invariant subspaces. Now we state our main theorems. According to [2], these results are established in [1]. However, since no publicly available version of [1] seems to exist, we provide here a complete and self-contained treatment in the setting of Toeplitz operators on the Hardy space.

Theorem 1. *Put $p(z, w) = z^k + w^l$. Then the von Neumann algebra $\mathcal{V}^*(p)$ defined on $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ is $*$ -isomorphic to $M_{kl}(\mathbf{C}) \oplus M_{kl}(\mathbf{C})$.*

Theorem 2. *Put $p(z, w) = z^k + w^l$. Then the minimal reducing subspaces of T_p in $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ are $[q]_{T_p}$ and $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$, where $q(z, w)$ is a polynomial in the form of*

$$q(z, w) = \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2}$$

and each a_{n_1, n_2} are complex numbers.

The present paper is organized as follows. We begin in Section 2 by investigating Theorem 2 under the specific conditions where $k = l = 1$, for which a complete proof is provided. Building on the insights from this case, Section 3 extends the analysis to present the full proof of the main theorem. We conclude in Section 4 with a discussion of future research directions.

2 The case $p(z, w) = z + w$

In the case where $k = l = 1$, Theorem 2 asserts the following:

Theorem 3. *The minimal reducing subspaces of T_{z+w} in $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ are $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$ and $[z - w]_{T_{z+w}}$.*

In order to prove Theorem 3, we introduce auxiliary spaces which are reducing subspaces of T_{z+w} .

Lemma 4. *Closed subspaces*

$$\mathcal{S} = \{f \in H^2(\mathbf{D}^2); \langle f, z^{n_1} w^{n_2} \rangle = \langle f, z^{n_2} w^{n_1} \rangle \text{ for all } n_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } n_2 \geq 0\}$$

and

$$\mathcal{A} = \{f \in H^2(\mathbf{D}^2); \langle f, z^{n_1} w^{n_2} \rangle = -\langle f, z^{n_2} w^{n_1} \rangle \text{ for all } n_1 \geq 0 \text{ and } n_2 \geq 0\}$$

are reducing subspaces of T_{z+w} .

Proof. It is clear that \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{A} are invariant under T_{z+w} .

We will show that \mathcal{S} is invariant under T_{z+w}^* . If f belongs to \mathcal{S} , then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T_{z+w}^* f, z^{n_1} w^{n_2} \rangle &= \langle f, z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2} \rangle + \langle f, z^{n_1} w^{n_2+1} \rangle \\ &= \langle f, z^{n_2} w^{n_1+1} \rangle + \langle f, z^{n_2+1} w^{n_1} \rangle \\ &= \langle f, T_{z+w}(z^{n_2} w^{n_1} + z^{n_2+1} w^{n_1}) \rangle \\ &= \langle T_{z+w}^* f, z^{n_2} w^{n_1} + z^{n_2+1} w^{n_1} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Hence we conclude that $T_{z+w}^* f$ belongs to \mathcal{S} . We also see that \mathcal{A} is invariant under T_{z+w}^* . \square

As a next step, we demonstrate, through a concrete example, how new symmetric polynomials can be generated from existing ones by employing the operator T_{z+w} together with its adjoint. Define an operator K on $H^2(\mathbf{T}^2)$ by $K = T_{z+w}^* T_{z+w}^2 - 3T_{z+w}$. A calculation shows that for $n_1 \geq 1$ and $n_2 \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} &K(z^{n_1} w^{n_2}) \\ &= T_{z+w}^*(z^{n_1+2} w^{n_2} + 2z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2+1} + z^{n_1} w^{n_2+2}) - 3z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2} - 3z^{n_1} w^{n_2+1} \\ &= z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2} + 2z^{n_1} w^{n_2+1} + z^{n_1-1} w^{n_2+2} \\ &\quad + z^{n_1+2} w^{n_2-1} + 2z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2} + z^{n_1} w^{n_2+1} - 3z^{n_1+1} w^{n_2} - 3z^{n_1} w^{n_2+1} \\ &= z^{n_1+2} w^{n_2-1} + z^{n_1-1} w^{n_2+2}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly we have $K(z^{n_1}) = z^{n_1-1} w^2$ and $K(w^{n_2}) = z^2 w^{n_2-1}$.

Hence for $N \geq 1$ we obtain

$$K(z^N \pm w^N) = z^{N-1} w^2 \pm z^2 w^{N-1}. \quad (1)$$

We note that the operator K facilitates the construction of symmetric polynomials of degree $N + 1$ from those of degree N , and importantly, it also enables the generation of alternating polynomials, which is essential for the development of the theory.

Based on the equation (1), we now demonstrate that the reducing spaces \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{A} are singly generated.

Proposition 5. $\mathcal{S} = [1]_{T_{z+w}}$.

Proof. From the definition of $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$, we see that $[1]_{T_{z+w}} \subset \mathcal{S}$. To prove $\mathcal{S} \subset [1]_{T_{z+w}}$, we will show that

$$z^n w^m + z^m w^n \in [1]_{T_{z+w}}$$

for all $n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$.

The proof proceeds by induction on N . Suppose that $z^n w^m + z^m w^n$ is in $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$ with $n + m \leq N, n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$.

From the equation (1), it follows that $z^{N-1}w^2 + z^2w^{N-1}$ belongs to $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$. Next, we have

$$T_{z+w}(z^{N-k}w^k + z^k w^{N-k}) = z^{N-k+1}w^k + z^k w^{N-k+1} + z^{N-k}w^{k+1} + z^{k+1}w^{N-k}$$

Substituting $k = 1$, we see that $z^N w + z w^N + z^{N-1}w^2 + z^2 w^{N-1}$ belongs to $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$. Hence we see that $z^N w + z w^N$ belongs to $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$. In the same way, repeated substitution for $k = 0, 2, 3, \dots$, together with the subtraction of functions already in $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$, ensures that the remaining functions

$$z^{N+1} + w^{N+1}, z^{N-2}w^3 + z^3 w^{N-2}, z^{N-3}w^4 + z^4 w^{N-3}, \dots$$

belongs to $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$ as well. We conclude that

$$z^n w^m + z^m w^n \in [1]_{T_{z+w}}$$

with $n + m = N + 1, n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 0$. The conclusion follows by induction. \square

We note that Lemma 6 can be established by applying the same technique used in the proof of Lemma 5.

Proposition 6. $[z - w]_{T_{z+w}} = \mathcal{A}$.

To prove that the reducing spaces $[1]_{T_{z+w}}$ and $[z - w]_{T_{z+w}}$ are minimal, we utilize the operator T introduced in [2]. The operator T is defined by the following equation;

$$T = T_p^* T_p - T_p T_p^*.$$

Easy calculations show that for any n_1, n_2 with $n_1 n_2 \neq 0$, then

$$T z^{n_1} w^{n_2} = 0, T z^{n_1} = z^{n_1}, T w^{n_2} = w^{n_2} \text{ and } T 1 = 2.$$

Moreover, we see that $T(z^{n_1} w^{n_2} - z^{n_2} w^{n_1}) = 0$ and $T(z^{n_2} - w^{n_2}) = z^{n_2} - w^{n_2}$ for any n_1, n_2 with $n_1 > n_2 > 0$, which are used in the proof of Proposition 8.

Proposition 7. *The reducing subspace \mathcal{S} is minimal.*

Proof. For any $f \in \mathcal{S}$, it is enough to show that $\mathcal{S} = [f]_{T_p}$. If f has no constant term, then we choose the smallest degree among all terms of f , which is denoted by N . Then we see that $(T_p^*)^N f(0, 0) \neq 0$. Put $F(z, w) = (T_p^*)^N f(z, w)$ and write

$$F(z, w) = \sum_{n_1=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_2=0}^{\infty} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2}$$

with $a_{0,0} \neq 0$. Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} TF(z, w) &= 2a_{0,0} + \sum_{n_1} a_{n_1,0} z^{n_1} + \sum_{n_2} a_{0,n_2} w^{n_2} \\ T^2 F(z, w) &= 4a_{0,0} + \sum_{n_1} a_{n_1,0} z^{n_1} + \sum_{n_2} a_{0,n_2} w^{n_2}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$1 = \frac{1}{2a_{0,0}} (T^2 - T)F \in [f]_{T_p}.$$

This implies that $\mathcal{S} \subset [f]_{T_p}$. Hence we conclude that $\mathcal{S} = [f]_{T_p}$. \square

Proposition 8. *The reducing subspace \mathcal{A} is minimal.*

Proof. For any $g \in \mathcal{A}$, it is enough to show that $\mathcal{A} = [g]_{T_p}$. If g does not contain the term $z - w$, then we choose the smallest degree among all terms of g , which is denoted by N' .

Then we see that $(T_p^*)^{N'-1}g$ contains the term $z - w$. Put $\tilde{G} = (T_p^*)^{N'-1}g$ and write

$$\tilde{G}(z, w) = \sum_{n_1 > n_2} a_{n_1, n_2} (z^{n_1} w^{n_2} - z^{n_2} w^{n_1})$$

with $a_{1,0} \neq 0$. Put $G = T\tilde{G}$. Then we write

$$G(z, w) = \sum_{n > 0} a_{n,0} (z^n - w^n).$$

We have

$$T_p^* T_p G(z, w) = a_{1,0} (z - w) + \sum_{n \geq 2} a_{n,0} (2z^n - 2w^n + z^{n-1}w - zw^{n-1})$$

and

$$TT_p^* T_p G(z, w) = a_{1,0} (z - w) + \sum_{n \geq 2} 2a_{n,0} (z^n - w^n).$$

Hence

$$z - w = \frac{1}{a_{1,0}} \{2G(z, w) - TT_p^* T_p G(z, w)\} \in [g]_{T_p}.$$

This implies that $\mathcal{A} \subset [g]_{T_p}$. Hence we conclude that $\mathcal{A} = [g]_{T_p}$. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. It is important to note that $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2) = [1]_{T_{z+w}} \oplus [z - w]_{T_{z+w}}$. We establish the conclusion by synthesizing Propositions 5, 6, 7, and 8. \square

3 The case $p(z, w) = z^k + w^l$

To begin with, we will provide specific examples of reducing subspaces of $T_{z^k+w^l}$. We define \mathcal{S}_p and \mathcal{A}_p as closed subspaces of functions in $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ that are defined by the conditions

$$\langle f, z^{a+n_1k} w^{b+n_2l} \rangle = \langle f, z^{a+n_2k} w^{b+n_1l} \rangle$$

and

$$\langle f, z^{a+n_1k} w^{b+n_2l} \rangle = -\langle f, z^{a+n_2k} w^{b+n_1l} \rangle$$

for all $0 \leq a < k$, $0 \leq b < l$, $n_1 \geq 0$ and $n_2 \geq 0$, respectively.

Proposition 9. *The following statements hold.*

(1) *Closed subspaces \mathcal{S}_p and \mathcal{A}_p are reducing subspaces of $T_{z^k+w^l}$.*

(2) *$[q]_{T_p} \subset \mathcal{S}_p$ and $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p} \subset \mathcal{A}_p$.*

In the same way as Lemma 4, we can prove (1) in Proposition 9. Moreover, it is clear that (2) in Proposition 9, since $q \in \mathcal{S}_p$ and $q(z^k - w^l) \in \mathcal{A}_p$.

From now on, we will prove Theorem 2, which generalizes Theorem 3. In the same way as [2], we introduce the operator \tilde{T} is defined by the following equality;

$$\tilde{T} = T_p^* T_p - T_p T_p^*,$$

Lemma 10 deals with the eigenvalues of the previously introduced operators and is deeply involved in the proof of Theorem 2.

Lemma 10. (1)

$$\tilde{T}(z^{n_1}w^{n_2}) = \begin{cases} 0 & (n_1 \geq k \text{ and } n_2 \geq l) \\ z^{n_1}w^{n_2} & (n_1 \geq k \text{ and } 0 \leq n_2 < l) \\ z^{n_1}w^{n_2} & (0 \leq n_1 < k \text{ and } n_2 \geq l) \\ 2z^{n_1}w^{n_2} & (0 \leq n_1 < k \text{ and } 0 \leq n_2 < l) \end{cases}$$

(2) For each $0 \leq n_1 < k$ and $0 \leq n_2 < l$, we obtain

$$\tilde{T}T_p^*T_p(z^{n_1}w^{n_2}(z^{Nk} - w^{Nl})) = \begin{cases} 2(z^{n_1}w^{n_2}(z^{Nk} - w^{Nl})) & (N \geq 2) \\ z^{n_1}w^{n_2}(z^k - w^l) & (N = 1) \end{cases}$$

The proof of Theorem 2 is analogous to the proof of Propositions 7 and 8;

Proof of Theorem 2. To begin with, we will prove that $[q]_{T_p}$ is minimal.

For any $f \in [q]_{T_p}$, it suffices to show that $[q]_{T_p} = [f]_{T_p}$. If f does not contain the term $z^{n_1}w^{n_2}$ ($0 \leq n_1 < k, 0 \leq n_2 < l$), then choose a natural number N_1 such that $(T_p^*)^{N_1}f$ contains these terms. Put $F = (T_p^*)^{N_1}f = F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4$, where

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(z, w) &= \sum_{m_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m_2=0}^{l-1} b_{m_1, m_2} z^{m_1} w^{m_2}, & F_2(z, w) &= \sum_{m_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m_2=l}^{\infty} b_{m_1, m_2} z^{m_1} w^{m_2}, \\ F_3(z, w) &= \sum_{m_1=k}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=0}^{l-1} b_{m_1, m_2} z^{m_1} w^{m_2}, & F_4(z, w) &= \sum_{m_1=k}^{\infty} \sum_{m_2=l}^{\infty} b_{m_1, m_2} z^{m_1} w^{m_2}. \end{aligned}$$

We compute

$$\tilde{T}F(z, w) = 2F_1 + F_2 + F_3 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{T}^2F(z, w) = 4F_1 + F_2 + F_3$$

Hence $\frac{1}{2}(\tilde{T}^2 - \tilde{T})F = F_1$, where

$$F_1(z, w) = \sum_{m_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{m_2=0}^{l-1} b_{m_1, m_2} z^{m_1} w^{m_2}$$

is in $[q]_{T_p}$. From the definition of $[q]_{T_p}$, F_1 must be the constant multiple of q . Hence we conclude that $q \in [f]_{T_p}$ and that $[q]_{T_p}$ is minimal.

Next, we will prove that $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$ is minimal.

For any $g \in [q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$, it suffices to show that $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p} = [g]_{T_p}$. If f does not contain the term $z^{n_1}w^{n_2}(z^k - w^l)$ ($0 \leq n_1 < k, 0 \leq n_2 < l$), then choose a natural number N_2 such that $(T_p^*)^{N_2}g$ contains these terms. Put $G = (T_p^*)^{N_2}g$. From Lemma 10, we see that

$$\tilde{T}G = \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2} (z^k - w^l) + \sum_{N=2}^{\infty} \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2} (z^{Nk} - w^{Nl})$$

and

$$\tilde{T}T_p^*T_p\tilde{T}G = \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2} (z^k - w^l) + 2 \sum_{N=2}^{\infty} \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2} (z^{Nk} - w^{Nl})$$

Put

$$G_1(z, w) = \sum_{n_1=0}^{k-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{l-1} a_{n_1, n_2} z^{n_1} w^{n_2} (z^k - w^l)$$

is in $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$. From the definition of $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$, G_1 must be the constant multiple of $q(z^k - w^l)$. Hence we conclude that $q(z^k - w^l) \in [g]_{T_p}$ and that $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$ is minimal. \square

Since the polynomial q in Theorem 2 consists of at most kl monomials, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 11. *The Hardy space $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ contains at most $2kl$ minimal reducing subspaces of T_p . More precisely, each of the spaces \mathcal{S}_p and \mathcal{A}_p contains at most kl minimal reducing subspaces.*

Finally we prove Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. $[q]_{T_p}$ and $[q(z^k - w^l)]_{T_p}$ are orthogonal minimal reducing subspaces of dimension kl , and that the restriction of T_p to each subspace generates the full matrix algebra, the von Neumann algebra generated by T_p is $*$ -isomorphic to $M_{kl}(\mathbf{C}) \oplus M_{kl}(\mathbf{C})$. \square

In particular, if $p(z, w) = z + w$, then the von Neumann algebra $\mathcal{V}^*(p)$ defined on $H^2(\mathbf{D}^2)$ is $*$ -isomorphic to $\mathbf{C} \oplus \mathbf{C}$.

4 Further remark

In conclusion, this preprint determines the structure of minimal reducing subspaces for Toeplitz operators whose symbols are of the form $z^k + w^l$. As a future direction, we intend to extend our investigation to Toeplitz operators with symbols of the symmetric form $z^k w^l + z^l w^k$.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

Declaration of Generative AI in Scientific Writing

During the preparation of this work, the author used generative AI tools, including Gemini 1.5 Pro (Google) and ChatGPT (GPT-5 mini, OpenAI), solely to improve English language quality and refine the manuscript's structure. The author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the publication.

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